

ROBOTS ARE INNOVATIVE FUTURE FOUNDATIONS

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Annotation. This the article current of the day evolving growing direction was robotics importance of them come exit dates and this with together thriving fine lines about explained.

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Annotation. This article explains the importance of robotics, which is a developing trend today, the history of their origin, as well as the stages of development.

Today, the world is evolving and improving day by day. Robots and technology have taken over almost half of the human way of life. No one today can imagine their lifestyle without the help of robots. Robots have entered our daily lives in such a way that they have become an integral part of us. In the 21st century, robots, or smart technologies, have taken on several functions in every family, with which we can communicate (telephone), store our belongings (safes), and watch entertaining

shows (television, social networks), and even when we don't have them we can trust our home.

In our time, robots are evolving and even being embodied in human form, and at the same time, it is becoming more and more popular to transfer human actions to them.

The term robot was first used in the play R.U.R (Rossum universal robots) by Czech writer Karel Chapek in 1920. The word is derived from the Czech word "gobot", which means a machine that moves like a human. The protagonists of the play were mechanically human-like in appearance, physically and intellectually superior to man. Chapek called them "robots." The word has squeezed out the term "android" (the word "android" has survived only in the name of mechanical dolls of the past) and has spread to all languages of the world. It should be noted that before that the term android was quite popular and common among people.

Over time, interest in these robots and research on them has grown significantly. The results of his research led to the creation and development of sciences such as artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence (AI) has allowed computers to study their experiments, adapt to given parameters, and perform tasks previously only possible for humans. In many cases of artificial intelligence - from computer chess players to unmanned vehicles - the ability to study deeply and process natural languages is crucial. Thanks to these technologies, computers can be trained to perform certain tasks by processing large amounts of data and identifying the data in them. It has been said that the first serious debates about artificial intelligence began with the advent of computers. The first serious scientific study of the possibility of a machine being intelligent was made by Alan Turing, a British physicist, and mathematician who was considered the founder of modern computer science. Turing offers several ideas to prove that artificial intelligence is possible or impossible in practice. "If a machine behaves like a creature that thinks in every way, it has to have intelligence," Turing said.

While there is debate about what machines can be called robots, it is argued that a typical robot should have the following qualities:

- Unnatural, that is, created by a conscious being.
- Can observe the environment (it is not necessary to observe visually; there may be other types of perception).
- Can interact with the environment.
- Able to make some smart decisions (independent or pre-programmed).
- Programmable.
- Can move with rotating or parallel axes.
- Can perform agile manipulations.
- Can demonstrate willpower (this quality is not important, zero applies to anthropomorphism).

Today, in a world where scientists also need to limit their time in the laboratory and maintain social distance from each other, robot scientist has emerged spontaneously.

“He doesn’t get bored, he doesn’t get tired, he works day and night, and he doesn’t need holidays,” Dr. Burger joked. On a more serious note, he said the robot changed the pace of research. “It can easily go through thousands of samples,” he said, “so it frees up my time to focus on innovation and new solutions.”

Like robotics designed for space exploration, such machines can perform more dangerous experiments - in a harsher laboratory environment or when using more toxic substances.

According to Deirdre Black, head of research and innovation at the British Chemical Society, British science needs to create new technologies in its infrastructure. “It’s about people using all of these digital technologies to move faster - exploring and innovating faster and exploring bigger and more complex issues like decarbonization, disease prevention and treatment and cleaning our air,” he told the BBC.

One of the characteristics of robots in today’s world is that they can replicate precise movements given in the same way. Such robots are also called manipulators. First-generation robots are used in various industries. In particular, the welding robot works at the Ford car plant in the United States and General Motors, on the

conveyors of car plants in Japan, the United States, France, Russia (Tolyatti). The robots are helping to make TV and radio equipment in Riga, refrigerators in Saratov, and agricultural machinery in Tashkent.

This means that the introduction of robots into our daily and social lives is aimed at the full development of humans and, in turn, alleviating our problems. People believe that robots will cover almost our entire lives in the future, and this, of course, can be a door to great results and achievements. Because, as mentioned above, robots are the main foundation for building the world of the future.

REFERENCES

1. “Artificial intellect” / T.A.Xo`jakulov, N.T.Malikova - Tashkent, Uzbekistan: “Aloqachi”, 2019. Pages 29-31.
2. Artificial intelligence. The basis of computational agents - David Pul, Alan McVorf it. Cambridge University Press - 2010 - 682 стр.
3. <https://community.uzbekcoders.en/post/sun-iy-intellect-what-which-in-the-field-most-necessary-5ebe4e949b2cf411ea60464d>
4. <https://www.bbc.com/news/science-environment-53029854?piano-modal>
5. https://www.orbit.uz/index.php?option=com_content&view=article&id=629:artificial-intelligence-thinking-machines-conscious-robots-about&catid=49:this-how-works&itemid=71